

Electrolytic Reduction of *m*-Dinitrobenzene to *m*-Phenylene Diamine

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Manuscript received 6 January 1976; revised 29 March 1976; accepted 1 April 1976

Electrolytic reduction of *m*-dinitrobenzene to *m*-phenylenediamine is compared with other chemical methods and advantages are discussed. Experiments with rotating and stationary cathodes have been carried out and the results presented. Experimental results of 150 ampere scale experiment has also been given. Depolarisation studies have been made and the results are presented.

m-PHENYLENE diamine finds its use in the dye industry and photographic industry. Chrysoidine and Bismarck Brown are the main dyes¹. It is a reagent for detecting nitrous acid and also finds use as textile developing agent. It also finds use in the manufacture of optical whiteners. Its demand is about 36 tons valued at Rs. 4 lakhs and it is likely to increase further². *m*-Phenylene diamine is manufactured chemically by reduction of *m*-dinitrobenzene with iron and hydrochloric acid³. Conditions must be strictly observed or otherwise azoxy compounds may be formed. If this happens the reduction is unsuccessful and should be discontinued. The trouble may also arise from a bad batch of iron emphasizing the need for testing each iron sample for its reactivity before purchasing it. Yield reported under best condition is 94.3% *m*-phenylene diamine was prepared from *m*-nitro aniline by catalytic reduction⁴. The yield was very low due to slight volatility of the nitro aniline. Electrolytic reduction of *m*-dinitrobenzene to *m*-phenylene diamine was studied by Bochringer and Sohne⁵. Their reported yield is 83%. Electrolytic preparation of *m*-phenylene diamine from *m*-nitro aniline using stannous chloride in hydrochloric acid medium has been studied and the reported yield⁶ is 98.7%. Bochringer and Sohne have used a solvent and the yield reported is also low. Evolution of chlorine gas is a problem in the electrolytic reduction of *m*-nitro aniline using hydrochloric acid as a medium. Many workers^{7,8} have reported the preparation of 2,4-diamino phenol starting from *m*-dinitrobenzene. Holleck and Schmidt⁹ have reported that they were able to observe the azo derivative by reducing *m*-dinitrobenzene at a mercury cathode. Dietz¹⁰ and Schultz¹¹ in their review have reported that compounds like phenylene dihydroxyl amine and nitrophenyl hydroxyl amine are formed along with *m*-phenylene diamine. Since it was observed from our studies that mono nitro compounds like nitrobenzene¹² and *p*-nitrophenol can be reduced to their amines in good yields, some studies were made with dinitro compound *m*-dinitrobenzene also and the results were encouraging.

Experimental

Some experimental set up as was used for the reduction of nitrobenzene to aniline was used¹². The cell consists of a 3 litre beaker with a wooden cover with provision for stationary electrode of copper, stirrer, thermometer, porous pot which is used as anode diaphragm, condenser with suction, etc. Copper cathode which is semi-circular in shape faces the anode. Anode is a perforated lead strip and has an area of 1.8 dm². Ceramic diaphragm is used to separate the anolyte from catholyte. The cell is kept in a water bath whose temperature can be controlled by external heating or cooling. Electrolytic reduction was carried out under the following conditions. The temperature was maintained between 70-90° as the solubility of *m*-dinitrobenzene is maximum at 100° about¹⁴ 0.2 g at 100°. The vapours from the cell was refluxed as *m*-dinitrobenzene and was volatile with steam.

Conditions :

Catholyte	1000 ml 20% sulphuric acid (V/V)
Cathode	Stationary copper of area 1.8 dm ²
Nitro compound taken	700 g
Temperature	80°-90°
Anolyte	180 ml 20% sulphuric acid (V/V)
Diaphragm	Ceramic
Current	30 A
Current density	16.7 A/dm ²
Cell voltage	5-6 V
Vol. of titanous sulphate solution added to catholyte	150 ml containing 10.2 g TiO ₂
Wt. of copper sulphate added to catholyte.	1 g

Results :

Wt. of nitro compound recovered,	149 g
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Wt. of <i>m</i> -phenylene-diamine sulphate recovered.	97.4 g of purity over 98%
Wt. of <i>m</i> -dinitrobenzene reduced.	551 g
Total <i>m</i> -phenylene diamine accounted.	326.4 g
Yield	92%
Current efficiency	98%
Energy consumption	18.5 kWh/kg of <i>m</i> -phenylene diamine.

Results :

Wt. of nitro compound recovered.	23 g
Wt. of nitro compound reduced.	27 g
Wt. of <i>m</i> -phenylene diamine estimated in the liquor	17 g
Yield	97.9%
No. of ampere hours	51
Current efficiency	99.2%

Reuse of electrolyte was studied by using the same electrolyte after removing solid *m*-phenylene diamine sulphate.

Same conditions as was used for previous experiment was observed and the results are as shown below:

Results :

Wt. of nitro compound taken.	1250(850+400) g**
Wt. of <i>m</i> -dinitrobenzene recovered.	8.54 g
Wt. of <i>m</i> -phenylene diamine sulphate recovered.	1466 g of purity over 98%
Wt. of <i>m</i> -phenylene diamine in solution.	38.75 g
Percentage of yield	99%
Current efficiency	98.7%
Energy consumption	18.7 kWh/kg of <i>m</i> -phenyl amine.

Electrolytic reduction of *m*-dinitrobenzene to *m*-phenylene diamine was also carried out under rotating copper cathode under the following conditions and the results were similar to that of stationary cathode.

Conditions :

Catholyte	1000 ml 20% of sulphuric acid (V/V).
Cathode	Rotating copper cathode of area 0.33 dm ² .
Current	8 A
Current density	24 A/dm ²
Nitro compound taken	50 g
Anolyte	180 ml 20% H ₂ SO ₄ (V/V)
Cell voltage	3-3.5V
Vol. of titanate sulphate solution added to catholyte.	150 ml containing 10.2 g of TiO ₂ .
Wt. of copper sulphate added to catholyte.	1 g

Electrolytic reduction of *m*-dinitrobenzene to *m*-phenylene diamine was carried out in 150 ampere scale in a copper vessel. The cell itself acts as a cathode and it is provided with a wooden cover with provision for mechanical stirrer, porous pot, thermometer and condenser with suction arrangements. The cell has a volume of 12 litres. The porous pot has a volume of 2 litres and the lead anode has an area of 10 dm². The experiment was carried out under the following conditions.

Conditions :

Volume of catholyte	5 lit 20% H ₂ SO ₄ (V/V) containing 50 g TiO ₂ as titanate sulphate.
Cathode	Stationary copper of area 20 dm ²
Nitro compound taken	1 kg
Temperature	70°-90°
Anolyte	2 lit. 20% H ₂ SO ₄ (V/V)
Diaphragm	Ceramic porous pot
Current	150 A
Current density	7.5 A/dm ²
Cell voltage	4.5-6 V
Copper sulphate added to catholyte.	5 g
Wt. of nitrocompound recovered.	Nil
Wt. of <i>m</i> -phenylene diamine estimated in solution.	740 g
Wt. of <i>m</i> -phenylene diamine theoretical.	743 g
Yield	100%
Quantity of current passed	1803 A.hrs.
Current efficiency	96.5%
Power consumed per kg of amine produced.	16.9 kWh

Depolarisation studies for the electro-reduction of m-dinitrobenzene in presence of titanate sulphate :

Depolarisation studies were made for the electro-reduction of titanate sulphate with and without *m*-dinitrobenzene at a stationary electrode under the same conditions at which the reduction of *m*-dinitrobenzene is carried out and the results are shown in Fig. 1. The studies were made to obtain the optimum current density range at which the reduction can be

**Same electrolyte was used twice and the figures within the bracket indicate the amount of nitrocompound added to each use.

carried out with minimum evolution of hydrogen so that the current efficiency can be maximum.

Fig. 1. Depolarisation studies for the electrolytic reduction of *m*-dinitrobenzene to *m*-phenylenediamine at 80°-90°

○ — ○ 20% H₂SO₄ (V/V)
 × — × 20% H₂SO₄ containing Ti(SO₄)₂
 △ — △ 20% H₂SO₄ + *m*-dinitrobenzene

From the figure it is observed that there is good depolarisation for the curve obtained by titanous sulphate alone at low current density ranges. It slowly decreases upto a certain current density range and then increases at high current densities.

For the curve obtained by titanous sulphate and *m*-dinitrobenzene together the slope of the curve remains almost same upto a current density of 11.75 A/dm². Afterwards the slope increases suddenly and remains same upto some current density value and again decreases after a current density of 35 A/dm². The first change in slope is due to evolution of hydrogen along with titanous sulphate reduction. The second change in slope may be erratic due to gas bubble formation at the electrode as the current density is too high to carry out any reduction. Another interesting observation here is that the potential corresponding to first change in slope of the curve is -0.02 V which is near the redox potential of the system Ti⁴⁺ + e ⇌ Ti³⁺ i.e., -0.06 V. It is evident that the Ti⁴⁺ and Ti³⁺ are in very good equilibrium upto a current density of 11.75 A/dm². Afterwards the potential gets shifted towards more negative value due to hydrogen evolution. Depolarisation also remains constant upto this current density value, viz., 0.06 V. One important observation from this study is that the depolarisation is independent of current density upto 11.75 A/dm² at a stationary copper electrode in presence of titanous sulphate.

Results and Discussions

Theoretically 44.67 hr are required to reduce 700 g *m*-dinitrobenzene if the current is 30 A. Hence it is observed that 0.004352 g nitro compound gets reduced for every second. The solubility¹⁴ of *m*-dinitrobenzene in water is 0.191 g at 100° and 0.0469 g at 50°.

Since *m*-phenylene diamine is isolated as sulphate it can be preserved for several months without appreciable change in colour. Experiments have proved that *m*-phenylenediamine can be directly coupled to diazonium salts when *m*-phenylenediamine is in the sulphate form. Under the above conditions it is possible to use the electrolyte several times by making slight adjustments in the acid concentration of the liquor which is used repeatedly.

Conclusion

It is observed that use of sulphate bath can give better efficiency than a chloride bath. Problems like chlorine evolution at the anode can be solved by the above method.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Shri A. Pourassamy, Junior Technical Assistant, National Aeronautical Laboratory, Bangalore for his contribution in this paper.

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